

The Roadmap of Geothermal Human Resources Development: A Synergies between Agencies under the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources

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ABSTRACT

Indonesia is known to have the most extensive geothermal reserves in the world. Therefore, the government continues to increase the role of geothermal energy as a power producer. This effort is due to Indonesia's energy demand has a significant increase while reducing dependence on expensive and environmentally unfriendly fossil fuels. Geothermal exploitation is an activity with a high risk, uses high technology, and requires a significant investment. This risk can be reduced by employing competent human resources. However, there has not been a complete roadmap for the development of geothermal human resources. This roadmap is needed by governments and industry to determine workforce needs and what competencies these workers must possess. The roadmap aims to reduce the mismatch between educational and training institutions and industry needs.

The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (MEMR), responsible for this industry, should prepare this roadmap and all stakeholders. The MEMR internal collaboration between institutions with geothermal tasks and functions underneath is an essential part of this roadmap creation. They are the Directorate General of EBTKE, Human Resources Development Agency of MEMR, Geological Agency, and Research and Development Agency of MEMR. This paper discussed these institutions' roles to map the extent of their programs in human resources development. Furthermore, this paper discussed what competency standards have been created and planned by the ministry. The geothermal development roadmap and support from international communities are also briefly deliberated. This paper aims to evaluate the current roadmap and its challenges to map the needs of competent geothermal human resources compatible with industry standards.

1. INTRODUCTION

The geothermal industry has long been operating in Indonesia since the 1960s. Nevertheless, until now, its contribution to the energy mix is still minimal. Until the end of 2019, the geothermal installed capacity was reported to be 2088.5 MW and MEMR (2019). This capacity is around 3% of the nearly 64.924,80 MW of electricity generating capacity in Indonesia, DGE (2019). The government has a high target for developing renewable energy in the future, including the geothermal industry, which is 23% the proportion of renewable energy in the energy mix of 2025 (NEP, 2017). With this high target, a large number of workers will be needed. Umam et al. (2018) estimated that more than 20,000 new workers would be needed by 2025 to pursue geothermal targets.

However, one of the main problems of geothermal energy in Indonesia is the availability of competent human resources that match the following industry needs. This problem is partly due to formal education graduates' unpreparedness to work directly in the geothermal industry. To prepare this much workforce, the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources supports by issuing national competency standards in geothermal energy. They were also preparing a roadmap for developing geothermal human resources.

With this roadmap, it is hoped that the geothermal human resource development plan will be more focused. This roadmap can be in the form of a short-term plan, a medium-term plan, or a long-term plan. This roadmap can be in the form of missions, programs, or even activities that must be carried out to achieve the existing goal.

It is also expected that policy discontinuity will not occur with the presence of the roadmap. A remark that highlighted in government policymaking is policy discontinuity. The typical problem in Indonesia is the change of government regimes and even officials' change to make an inconsistent policy. This inconsistency also happened in the development of geothermal energy. In addition to its changing policies, its development targets have also changed. Both targets are formal and informal.

1.1 Geothermal in Indonesia

Indonesia has succeeded in becoming the second-largest geothermal power-producing country globally, shifting the Philippines' position with a capacity of 2088.5 MW until December 2019, MEMR (2019). The latest capacity addition comes from the Muara Laboh Geothermal power plant (GPP) with 85 MW capacity. Another accomplishment is GPP Lumut Balai Unit 1, carried out by PT Pertamina Geothermal Energy with a 55 MW capacity. At present, Indonesia's installed geothermal capacity is only below that of the United States, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Geothermal installed capacity in the World (MW) (ThinkGeoEnergy, 2019; MEMR, 2019)

However, NEP (2017) emphasized that geothermal plant capacity is targeted to increase to reach 7,200 MW in 2025. The 2025 energy mix target stated that the portion of renewable energy had been set at 23%. The government's efforts are to take strategic steps by assigning several geothermal developers to accelerate geothermal energy development. A list of GPP in Indonesia until 2019 is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. List of GPPs operating in Indonesia, DG-NREEC (2019a) and PabumNews (2019)

No	Power Plant	Operator	Capacity
1	GPP Sibayak	PT Pertamina Geothermal Energy	12 MW
2	GPP Sarulla	Sarulla Operation Ltd.	330 MW
3	GPP Ulubelu	PT Pertamina Geothermal Energy	220 MW
4	GPP Salak	PT Star Energy Geothermal Salak. Ltd.	377 MW
5	GPP Wayang Windu	Star Energy Geothermal Wayang Windu	227 MW
6	GPP Patuha	PT Geo Dipa Energy	55 MW
7	GPP Kamojang	PT Pertamina Geothermal Energy	235 MW
8	GPP Darajat	Star Energy Geothermal Drajat	270 MW
9	GPP Dieng	PT Geo Dipa Energy	60 MW
10	GPP Karaha	PT Pertamina Geothermal Energy	30 MW
11	GPP Matalako	PT Perusahaan Listrik Negara	2.5 MW
12	GPP Ulumbu	PT Perusahaan Listrik Negara	10 MW
13	GPP Lahendong	PT Pertamina Geothermal Energy	120 MW
14	GPP Muara Laboh	PT Supreme Energy Muara Laboh (SEML)	85 MW
15	GPP Lumut balai	PT Pertamina Geothermal Energy	55 MW
Total			2088.5 MW

1.2 National Energy General Plan

The National Energy Policy is explained in Government Regulation No. 79 of 2014. Further, the policy is outlined in the Presidential Regulation Number 22 of 2017 Concerning the National Energy Plan (NEP). The National Energy Council initially drafts NEP. They have analyzed a series of the model as a reference for energy development in Indonesia. One of the national energy policy targets is the achievement of an optimal primary energy mix in 2025. The target has set the role of energy new and renewable energy at least 23%, the role of petroleum is less than 25%, the role of coal is at least 30% natural gas at least 22%. Further, the role of new energy and renewable energy is at least 31% in 2050 as long as its economy is fulfilled. Moreover, the role of petroleum is expected less than 20%, the role of coal is at least 25%, and natural gas is at least 24% (NEP, 2017).

The geothermal potential of 29.5 GW is highly anticipated as the source of and renewable energy (EBT) in the future. The DEN estimated that geothermal power plants' development should reach 7,241.5 MW in 2025 and 17,546 MW in 2050.

The government has prepared the NEP to target energy independence and national energy security. This target can be achieved by realizing the development of domestic technology, the energy industry, and energy services capabilities to be independent and increase human resources' capacity to create jobs. One of the efforts is to increase the domestic capability to support geothermal exploration and electricity supporting industries. Also, it strengthens the field of research, development, and implementation of energy through the preparation and improvement of human resource capabilities and the application of technology to the application of energy-saving technologies.

1.3 Electricity Supply Plan

The NEP is further specified in the General Electricity Supply Plan of the state-owned electricity company (PLN). Every year, PLN issues the plan to be used as a reference for electricity development over the next ten years. The latest plan is the General Plan for Electric Power Supply 2019-2028.

Indonesia's fuel mix target in 2028 states that the composition of electricity production is projected to be composed of 54.4% coal, 22% natural gas (including LNG), 9.6% geothermal, 10.9% hydropower, 0.4% fuel, and 2.6% other energy sources (PLN, 2019).

The additional plan for Indonesia's electricity generation capacity for 2019-2028 is 56.6 GW or 5.6 GW per year. This generation consists of coal-fired power plants, which will dominate the types of power plants to be built, reaching 27.1 GW or 48.0% and PLTGU with a capacity of 9.1 GW or 16.2% and PLTG 3.3 GW or 5.8%. For Renewable, the largest share comes from hydroelectric and micro hydropower with a total capacity of 9.7 GW or 17.2%, followed by geothermal with 4.6 GW or 8.2%. Other renewable energy sources contribute 2.6 GW or 4.5%.

2. THE ROLE OF MINISTRY OF ENERGY AND MINERAL RESOURCES

The MEMR issued a strategic plan for 2015-2019 through the Decree of the Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources No. 13 of 2015. The target of electricity generation from EBT was 16,996 MW in 2019, including 3,195 MW from Geothermal Energy, MEMR, (2015). This target was proven not to be achieved with the current installed capacity of only 2088.5 MW. Regulations that are not friendly to investment in geothermal development and the lack of competent human resources are accused of being an obstacle to Indonesia's geothermal industry.

According to Smillie et al. (2015), the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources has prepared steps to develop a competent workforce, namely;

- a. Ensuring education and training are competency-based.
- b. Increase the number of worker certifications
- c. Improve the competence of teachers
- d. Accreditation of training providers
- e. Collaboration with all stakeholders
- f. Improving the quality of education and training infrastructure
- g. Increasing the scope of Indonesian national competency work standards (NCS)
- h. Utilize CSR funds to provide skilled labor

Moreover, several departments in the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources in geothermal development are briefly discussed below.

2.1 The Directorate General of New, Renewable Energy, and Energy Conservation (DG-NREEC) Represented by the Geothermal Directorate.

The role of the Geothermal Directorate in developing human resource competencies is the preparation, development, and implementation of the NCS. The NCS application is divided into two focuses: a focus on the core competencies of the geothermal sector and the focus of competencies in the supporting sector. The Geothermal Directorate will also hold certification at the expert level. Until now, there are 3 (three) NCS fields of geothermal that have been approved by the Ministry of Manpower, namely NCS geothermal geologists, geothermal geochemists, and geothermal geophysics.

In addition to NCS in geothermal, there are already three Special Competency Standards, namely the Junior Operational Supervisor (POP), Intermediate Operational Supervisor (POM), and Senior Operations Supervisor (POU). Until 2019, the geothermal directorate data shows that about 1,548 persons have been certified, 1,230 at the POP level, 233 at the POM level, and 85 at the POU level, DG-NREEC (2019b).

2.2 Geological Agency represented by the Center for Coal and Geothermal Resources

The center was initially known as the Center for Geological Resources to inventory and explore geospatial prospecting areas. This agency is also tasked with compiling geological resource balance sheets, thematic mapping of the potential of geological resources, and providing recommendations on using potential geological resources.

In collaboration with another research agency, the center also conducts research and investigations in geothermal resources, engineering design, and modeling. This center operates several research facilities and infrastructure to assist the needs of geothermal industries.

The inventory results, general investigation, and geothermal exploration activities by PSDMBP are published as official releases from the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, especially as the basis for economic calculations of geothermal working areas.

2.3 Research and Development Agency represented by the Research and Development Center for Electricity, Renewable Energy, and Energy Conservation

This center is a technology research and development unit established in 2002 focused on new and renewable energy, including geothermal. This institution has several experts in the geothermal field, such as geothermal engineers and geologists. During this time, they have collaborated with other centers, universities, and geothermal companies in Indonesia. The services provided to the public include expertise services such as surveying and data analysis.

The center is also carrying out geological work such as rock sampling, petrophysical analysis of reservoir rock, and determining rock age (dating). They also do geochemical work, such as water sampling for mineral analysis. In the geophysical area, the center is conducting MT, AMT, CSAMT, IP, TDEM / FDEM, and Resistivity. They are also carrying research on reservoir modeling based on 3G Data Analysis (Geology, Geophysics, Geochemistry) using well sim and TOUGH2 software.

Some of the projects that have been implemented are the Kamojang geothermal reservoir simulation, Lahendong field geothermal reservoir simulation, Sibayak field reservoir characteristics. They also did the Wellbore Darajat field simulation using well sim software, Geothermal reservoir simulation training, and greenfield geothermal reservoir simulation.

2.4 Human Resources Development Agency represented by the Human Resource Development Center for Electricity, New Energy, Renewable Energy and Energy Conservation (HRDC-ENREEC) and the Center for Oil and Gas Human Resource Development (HRDC-OG)

HRDC-ENREEC is a training center under the ministry responsible for human resources development in the field of geothermal energy as part of renewable energy sources. However, due to the wide range of responsibilities for this center, training is aimed more at downstream industries and power plants. The training conducted includes technical training for geothermal working areas, the introduction of work budgets and geothermal expenditure plans, and specialized HSE geothermal inspection training. The center also has regular geothermal supervisor training.

Another training center, HRDC-OG, is also involved in developing geothermal human resources, especially training and geothermal drilling certification. The center provides around 30 drilling training and certification annually. The participants are commonly prospective workers and employees with floorman, derrickmen, driller, and toolpushers positions. This training generally includes upstream oil and gas activities; well control techniques, BOP equipment, drilling and engineering equipment, and drilling safety.

HRDC-OG conducted training at the managerial level for Geothermal Well Drilling in 2017. This training is a pilot program funded by New Zealand's Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade (MFAT) in collaboration with HRDC-OG for drilling engineers and supervisors. PPSDM Migas had conducted Operation Maintenance Training for a geothermal company in 2018. The training duration was two and a half months and attended by 23 trainees. This program is a pilot project and is expected to be followed by further training with improved facilities and trainers.

3. THE NATIONAL COMPETENCY STANDARD FOR GEOTHERMAL

The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources has taken a role in developing the Indonesian National Work Competency Standards (NCS) on the geothermal field under the Indonesian National Qualification Framework (IQF). IQF is a bridge between industry and education. For geothermal energy, currently, there are Special Competency Standards for geothermal operations supervisors and three NCS on the upstream geothermal, namely NCS Geothermal Geologist, Geothermal Geochemist, and Geothermal Geophysicist.

3.1 Geology, Geochemistry, Geophysics (3G)

The newly established NCS in 3G is intended to strengthen the domestic human resources' role for more accurate search and determination of geothermal resources. The role of geologists, geophysics, and geochemists is needed in the initial stages of development, namely preliminary, exploration and drilling surveys, and when the power plant is in operation.

In the preliminary survey stage, geologists are required to identify geological settings, types of geothermal potential. They assess the evidence of geothermal potential to guide further activities. Monitoring data from existing geothermal areas also need to be collected by aerial imaging or remote sensing from satellites. Further, geologists, geochemists, and geophysicists must be able to collect geoscience data by active surface and subsurface surveys to minimize uncertainty in the exploration phase. They must also be able to provide primary environmental data and assist with monitoring throughout the project's life by integrating all aspects of geoscience-related to geothermal systems.

The geoscientist should also be able to assist and oversee the drilling process. They also analyze and interpret geological logging and cores to determine well productivity, drilling depth, and estimate corrosion risk. Moreover, the geoscientist is responsible for

monitoring surface activity, potential contaminants (water and gas), down-hole surveys, geochemical and geophysical analysis in the operation and maintenance phase.

3.2 Onshore Drilling

Drilling competency standards have been applied in Indonesia since 2007. Even though their applications are still limited to oil and gas drilling, the scope includes geothermal and hydrocarbon drilling. The competency section for both fields can facilitate labor transfer from one sector to another, Umam et al. (2018). On the other hand, qualification holders cannot be directly employed in the geothermal sector, despite having qualifications. This problem is due to the competency units in this standard are developed from the oil and gas sector. Another advantage of using only one standard is centralized training and certification for workers. However, such a system can limit the proliferation of labor needs in a short period. Therefore, this needs to be improved by improving the competency-based capacity building system in the future.

One other specific competency standard prepared by the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources is the standard for steam field operators. In addition to the two existing competency standards, power plant operators are required to have an Electric Power Engineering Competency Standard certificate issued by the Directorate General of Electricity. These competency standards generally aim to ensure a competent workforce in providing reliable, safe, and environmentally friendly electricity.

4. THE DIRECTION OF GEOTHERMAL DEVELOPMENT

4.1 Geothermal Development Roadmap

The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources already has a Geothermal Development Roadmap 2007-2025. Initially, the geothermal development target was 9,500 MW up to 2025. In order to achieve this, a master plan or Indonesian geothermal development plan was made in 2007 by the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), Nugraha (2007). The geothermal development roadmap becomes one of the contents in the attachment to Presidential Regulation No. 5/2006 concerning the National Energy Policy. Until 2009, the roadmap is planned that geothermal will be developed at 9,500 MW up to 2025.

However, in 2010 the 10,000 MW Electricity Development Acceleration Program was issued. This program is based on Presidential Regulation No. 4 of 2010. This program is often called the Phase II Fast Track program (Second FTP Program). With this program, regions in the geothermal development master plan are added to the FTP program regions. This program is the second phase of the program. In the first phase of the program, the program's plants are 100% from fossil plants. Whereas in this second stage, the program emphasizes more on the use of renewable energy. So that the 10,000 MW was initially expected to come mostly from renewable energy, the Geothermal energy at that time, initially allocated up to 6,000 MW. However, after being identified, geothermal is planned to be developed, included in the program by only 4,925 MW. Then in 2011, to strengthen the utilization of new renewable energy, the DG-NREEC was formed.

With the new unit, geothermal development targets are aligned with the 25/25 vision. What is meant by vision 25/25 is the proportion of new renewable energy use by 25% in 2025. With this vision, geothermal is expected to contribute, even more, amounting to 12,000 MW. With a more aggressive vision, additional areas will be developed. The region originates from the geothermal and FTP II development master plan plus areas to meet the 25/25 vision target.

In 2015, the 35,000 MW Power Plant Development Program was issued based on the Decree of the Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources (MEMR) Number 74 of 2015 concerning Ratification of the 2015-2024 Electric Power Supply Business Plan. The geothermal portion increases 1,200 MW of the amount of 35,000 MW to the existing installed capacity. Nugraha et al. (2017) estimated that the reduction in geothermal development targets from 12,000 MW ambitions in 2011 to 7,100 MW was even only an increase of 1,200 MW in the 35,000 MW program due to several factors. One of the factors is that the plan to develop new GPPs, almost all of them experience delays and uncertainties. Thus, the new GPP has not been a priority.

4.2 Human Resources Development by Universities

The role of universities in developing geothermal energy in Indonesia is not yet significant. Only a few universities have geothermal departments or geothermal research centers. At present, most employees of geothermal companies generally do not have a formal geothermal education background. Prospective employees from various educational backgrounds, then the company provides specialized training for geothermal competencies. Furthermore, it is expected that there will be a match between university graduates and the geothermal industry's needs.

Institut Teknologi Bandung (ITB) is the only university that offers a four-semester master's geothermal program. This program is under the Faculty of Mining and Petroleum Technology. This program covers a wide area of geothermal energy exploration, exploitation, utilization, management, economics, and the environment. ITB also offers short courses to support geothermal drilling development since 1994, when ITB collaborated with the Geothermal Institute, University of Auckland, Saptadji (2010). This short course is 3 to 15 days long. It is available to the public, which is divided into engineering and geoscience groups.

In addition to ITB, Universitas Gajah Mada (UGM) also runs geothermal basic and advanced courses in collaboration with the University of Auckland and GNS Science. This course is generally held at the request of a geothermal company with a focus on geoscience.

A master's program with a choice of geothermal focus can also be taken at the Universitas Indonesia (UI) and Institut Teknologi Surabaya (ITS). UI offers Master Program with a focus on Geothermal Energy Exploration under the Department of Physics. Whereas ITS offers a Master Program in Geothermal Engineering in the Department of Geomatics Engineering, under the Faculty of Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering. In addition to the two universities, although not specifically in geothermal training, Diponegoro University (Undip) has offered a Masters in Energy program since 2014. Undip also has a geothermal research center under the Faculty of Science and Mathematics.

4.3 International Support

Human resources development for Indonesia's geothermal industry has been assisted by international assistance such as GEOCAP, USAID, NZSTIGS, and SATREPS. The Indonesia-Netherlands Geothermal Capacity Building Program (GEOCAP) is an international collaboration between Indonesian and Dutch institutions. Some of the institutions involved include Twente University, INAGA / API, TNO - Dutch Organization for Applied Scientific Research, ITB, Delft Technical University (TUDelft), UI, UGM, Utrecht University, IF Technology, DNV-GL Energy, and Well Engineering Partners (WEP).

The program also aims to support the Indonesian government to increase the utilization of geothermal resources by developing a subsurface database, research, education, and training. The Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs funds GEOCAP activities. GEOCAP also collaborates with various geothermal stakeholders in Indonesia to transfer knowledge and solve common problems.

Further, The United States Agency for International Development (USAID) also run some project for Geothermal Education Capacity Building, such as a university partnership between the University of Southern California (USC) and ITB from 2012 to 2015 with support from Star Energy. USAID has also worked with the Indonesian Geothermal Association (INAGA) from 2011 to 2014 to provide a geothermal Human Resources program. The program includes a master's degree program, trainer training, and an introductory geothermal program.

The New Zealand Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade (MFAT) regularly provides technical assistance and capacity building to accelerate Indonesia's geothermal development. The program offered is in the form of a Higher Education scholarship through the NZAS scheme and short training in the New Zealand Support for Training in Geothermal Support (NZSTIGS) scheme. MFAT was also signed an MoU with MEMR on September 5, 2018, to develop and provide practical training for technicians and geothermal operators for the next five years. Under this program, PPSDM KEBTKE organized the Training for the Trainers Mastery Level (TTT) with instructors from the Waikato Institute of Technology (WINTEC).

Finally, the Science and Technology Research Partnership for Sustainable Development (SATREPS) is a collaborative program between the Japan Science and Technology Agency (JST) and the Japan Agency for Medical Research and Development (AMED). It is supported by the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) to promote international joint research. This program aims to address global problems that need to be addressed by the international community and produce research results that are socially and economically beneficial for the future for local and global communities. One of the projects implemented is the project for Technology Development of Steam-spot Detection and Sustainable Resource Use for Large Enhancement of Geothermal Power Generation in Indonesia, Beneficial and Advanced Geothermal Use System (BAGUS). This project is a joint research project between ITB and Kyoto University.

5. THE ROADMAP OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN GEOTHERMAL

The roadmap's preparation should follow the assessment stage, identify the desired conditions, identify problems, and plan for action. These stages will be discussed briefly in this chapter.

5.1 Geothermal Workforces

Jennejohn (2010) researched in the United States to calculate the needs for geothermal labor. He found that for every megawatt of electricity produced from geothermal energy, it takes around 4.25 people full-time positions. The workforce requirements include geologists, geophysicists, geochemists, drillers, technicians, hydrologists, and other skilled personnel (Smillie et al.,2015). This calculation is for both the exploration phase and in the operation and maintenance phase.

Data from the geothermal directorate (2019) shows that in 2019, there were 7610 workers in Indonesian geothermal companies with a comparable power of 1948.5 MW, as shown in Figure 2. The data is shown in Figure 3; increasing the geothermal workforce in Indonesia shows that the average workforce needs are around three people for every MW generated. Thus, with an average increase of 150 MW per year, 450 workers are needed per year. This increase should be the concern of the government and stakeholders in preparing this workforce.

Figure 2. Geothermal workforce trends compared with installed capacity 2011 – 2018, DG-NREEC (2019c)

5.2 Current Roadmap

The Directorate of Geothermal has designed a master plan to develop human resources in the geothermal sector. The plan is divided into three stages. The stages increase geothermal awareness in the education, connect and match steps between research and industry, and build resource competence human power. In the road map, the years 2012 to 2016 are categorized as awareness years, 2017 to 2019 is the link and match year. While the years 2019 to 2025 are the building competence human resources period.

The stage of increasing geothermal awareness in higher education is realized by introducing geothermal activities to universities. This activity has been started in 2012 through the Geothermal Going to Campus (GGtC) Program. This program is also one of the government's efforts to bring geothermal energy closer to education. This GGtC has been carried out at several universities with subjects including the linking & matching stage. This stage is an effort to bridge the needs of industry and schools by applying NCS in the world of education and optimization of research and development through collaboration between universities, government, and industry, Umam et al. (2019).

Several universities that have been involved in the GGtC program are the Surabaya Institute of Technology (ITS), University of North Sumatra (USU), Trisakti University, UNILA, and Diponegoro University (UNDIP). The program was also introduced at Sriwijaya University (UNSRI), Andalas University (UNAND), Mataram University, Medan Institute of Technology, UNSRAT, UPN, UNSYAH, Jenderal Soedirman University (UNSOED), Jambi University, Nusa Cendana University, UNPAD, and Hasanuddin University (UNHAS).

The GGtC generally consists of two activities, namely general studies and project case studies. The general study, called the General Class, provides lecturers and students with a general understanding of geothermal in several subjects. On the other hand, the project case, also called the special class, is a simulation to evaluate the stages to develop geothermal potential from a subsurface investigation to project financial examination.

5.3 Challenges

Currently, there is an irony in the geothermal industry employment. The business entities have difficulty to find competent workers. At the same time, universities complain that their graduates are difficult to find a job. Thus, many companies proposed to be able to use foreign workers to overcome this labor shortage.

Hence, there is an asynchronous between the world of education and the world of work. The education products have not matched the requirements of the industrial world. Formally, the KKKNI will be the liaison and a media for linking and matching the two.

More socialization and training for schools and communities, especially around geothermal work areas, is essential to overcome this challenge. Also, adjustments to tertiary education curricula focused on geothermal must be dynamic; curriculum adjustments must follow any change in industry needs.

The roadmap should be able to adjust according to the WKP development schedule conducted by the government. The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources must also continue to harmonize the policymaking with the implementation of the IQF. Hence, the determination of learning outcomes or training and certification based on competency standards can be synchronized with industry needs.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The Indonesian government has set a high target in the development of the geothermal industry. Various programs have also been carried out to support the targets set, including human resource development. However, internal coordination within the government is still ineffective and impacts the length of the inhibiting bureaucracy. One proof is that after operating for more than 50 years, there are only three competency standards explicitly issued for workers in the geothermal industry. This problem is also coupled with the very lack of training and certification, especially at the operator level.

However, the government's acceleration efforts, especially the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, in collaboration with other ministries and stakeholders these days need to be appreciated. The roadmap that has been made by the Directorate-General of EBTKE can be continued with more concrete and detailed steps. It is proposed that the roadmap development is not rigid, so it is difficult to reach the target. The roadmap should be adapted to the actual conditions that occur dynamically and be supported by policy units2 under the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources.

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